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Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D2.6 – Functional and Non-Functional Specifications I

WP2 Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User
Scenarios in iHelp

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Table of Contents

- Executive summary 6
- 1 Introduction..... 7
- 2 iHelp Platform Overview 8
 - 2.1 Architecture..... 8
 - 2.1.1 Internal components 9
 - 2.1.2 Components off-the-shelf 10
- 3 Functional Specification 12
 - 3.1 API documentation 12
 - 3.2 Use cases 14
 - 3.3 iHelp components interactions 15
 - 3.3.1 Advice follow-up..... 15
 - 3.3.2 Advice review 17
 - 3.3.3 Caption of profiling characteristics..... 17
 - 3.3.4 Communication of risk 18
 - 3.3.5 Data visualization 19
 - 3.3.6 Develop risk prediction model 20
 - 3.3.7 Elevated risk detected 21
 - 3.3.8 Ingest tests and samples results..... 22
 - 3.3.9 Primary data ingestion 22
 - 3.3.10 Secondary data ingestion 27
 - 3.3.11 Monitoring..... 29
 - 3.3.12 Plan visit/control 30
 - 3.3.13 Request tests and samples 31
 - 3.3.14 Risk assessment..... 32
 - 3.3.15 Risk mitigation delivery 34
 - 3.3.16 Risk mitigation/treatment planning 35
 - 3.4 Traceability matrix..... 36
- 4 Non-Functional specifications 42
 - 4.1 Security & Privacy 42
 - 4.2 Scalability 42
 - 4.3 Maintainability..... 42
 - 4.4 Reliability 43

- 4.5 Other..... 43
- 5 Conclusions and future work 44
- Bibliography 45
- List of Acronyms 46
- Annex A. API Documentation 47
 - A.1 Data Connector 47
 - A.2 Data Gateway..... 54
 - A.3 Data Cleaner..... 55
 - A.4 Data Qualifier 55
 - A.5 Data Harmoniser 56
 - A.6 HRR Importer 57
 - A.7 Secondary Data Pre-processor 57
 - A.8 Personalised Predictor 67
 - A.9 Analytics Workbench - Model Library..... 69
 - A.10 Social Analyser 84
 - A.11 Monitoring and Alerting..... 99
 - A.12 Big Data Platform 110

List of Figures

Figure 1: iHelp Architecture (Mel 21).....	9
Figure 2: Advice follow-up activity diagram.....	16
Figure 3: Advice review activity diagram	17
Figure 4: Caption of profiling characteristics activity diagram.....	18
Figure 5: Communication of risk activity diagram.....	19
Figure 6: Data visualization activity diagram.....	20
Figure 7: Develop risk prediction model activity diagram	21
Figure 8: Elevated risk detected activity diagram	22
Figure 9: Primary data ingestion - step 1 activity diagram.....	23
Figure 10: Primary data ingestion - step 2 activity diagram.....	24
Figure 11: Primary data ingestion - step 3 activity diagram.....	25
Figure 12: Primary data ingestion - step 4 activity diagram.....	26
Figure 13: Final step of primary data ingestion activity diagrams	27
Figure 14: Secondary data ingestion - step 1 activity diagram	28
Figure 15: Secondary data ingestion - step 4 activity diagram	29
Figure 16: Monitoring activity diagram.....	30
Figure 17: Plan a visit or control activity diagram.....	31
Figure 18: Request tests and samples activity diagrams.....	32
Figure 19: Risk assessment activity diagrams	33
Figure 20: Risk mitigation delivery activity diagram	35
Figure 21: Risk mitigation/treatment planning activity diagram	36
Figure 22: Use Case/Methods Matrix	37

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the first release of the functional and non-function specifications of the iHELP solution, that will guide the development activities throughout the project, in order to achieve a consensus on what the iHelp platform will offer. This has a two-fold advantage as it will let the developers know what to build and the users what they will get.

These specifications explain how the requirements provided by the pilots and the technical partners will be fulfilled by the iHelp platform and provide a detailed definition of the functionalities/behaviours of the iHelp components and the interactions among them. Details on the design of the components are outlined in the related deliverables and are out of the scope of this document.

This work started from the outcomes of the requirements elicitation and architectural design, specifically the requirements in D2.1 – State of the art and requirements analysis I (M., M., P. + 21) and the architecture in D2.4 – Conceptual model and reference architecture I (Mel 21). Use cases reported in D2.1 have been analyzed to identify the iHelp components functions needed to satisfy them. The architecture has been examined to understand the role and objective of each component, and the technical specification has been produced for the most mature components at the current stage of the project, while the overall platform will be designed incrementally in accordance to the progresses of the project, and documented in the final version of the present report. Technical partners responsible for the components have been provided with a template and guidelines facilitating the production of the technical specifications and API documentation. Connection mechanisms, data flows and control flows have been discussed and clarified during frequent brainstorming involving all interested parties. Requirements specified in D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21) have been reviewed to derive the non-functional specifications.

The next version of this deliverable D2.7 – Functional and Non-Functional Specifications II, expected at M20, will report the functional and non-functional specifications of the whole iHelp platform and components.

1 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe the initial functional and non-functional specifications of the iHelp platform, with the objective of having a common reference of the functionalities offered by the platform, useful for both developers and users of the system. These specifications illustrate how the iHelp platform satisfies the requirements and accurately define the functionalities/behaviours of the iHelp components, thus directing the development activities. Hence, this report focuses on the specification of the necessary assets enabling the components interactions and the usage of the system, the interfaces of each component and the communication protocols. Nevertheless, single components and services are here considered as black-boxes and the details of their internal design are reported in the related deliverables and are out of the scope of the present document.

The inputs for the specifications were of the results of the requirements elicitation and architectural design. The collection of user and technical requirements, provided by the use case partners and the technical contributors of the project in deliverable D2.1 – State of the art and requirements analysis I (M., M., P. + 21), is a key input for the specification of the overall architecture by identifying the components, their functionalities and interconnection, as well as ensuring their coherency with the requirements.

The iHelp platform development follows an incremental approach: the functionality of the system is produced and delivered through iterative cycles and in small portions at a time (increments). In this way developers can benefit from what learnt during the implementation and usage of earlier parts/versions. At each iteration, requirements are revised, design is modified, new functional capabilities can be added and new parts of the system are implemented.

In the initial phase of the project, the collection, analysis and elicitation of the first version of the requirements of the iHelp platform have been reported in deliverable D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21), that was analysed to derive the components constituting the first release of the reference architecture, outlined in deliverable D2.4 – Conceptual model and reference architecture I (Mel 21). Both deliverables have been useful to gather the specifications described in this document.

This deliverable, being submitted at M10, represents the first release of the functional and non-functional specifications and focuses mainly on the set of components that will be implemented at this stage. The second and final release D2.7 – Functional and Non-Functional Specifications II, expected at M20, will be delivered after the update and refine of the requirements in deliverable D2.2 – State of the art and requirements analysis II (M12) and the final version of reference architecture will be released in D2.5 – Conceptual model and reference architecture II (M18).

This document is organized as follows:

- Section 1 reports the present introduction to the document.
- Section 2 remarks the iHelp reference architecture and the components being part of it, highlighting among them the software components that are part of the current specification.
- Section 3 describes the programming interfaces, the interactions among components to fulfil the requirements and map the requirements to the functionalities provided by the components.
- Section 4 is focused on non-functional specifications.
- Section 5 concludes the documents and describes the future work.

2 iHelp Platform Overview

iHelp aims at early identifying and mitigating the risks associated with Pancreatic Cancer (PC) by applying advance AI-based learning and decision support techniques on the historic (primary) data of Cancer patients, integrated with (secondary) data gathered through the mobile and wearable applications (concerning lifestyle, behavioural, social interactions and response to targeted prevention and intervention measures).

The expected usage of the iHelp platform from a user perspective, detailed in D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21), includes:

- identification of people at high risk of PC and facilitate cancer risk mitigation
- evaluation of the risk of toxicity for patients already diagnosed with PC and undergoing radiotherapy or chemoradiation
- derivation of the relationships between the known risks and discover new ones if there are new factors that can affect negative or positive modulation
- facilitation of the decision-making process into the early diagnosis of those conditions that are elevating the health risk level for PC development, as well as diagnosing the PC in early stage of development
- application of data analytics, AI-based algorithms or deep learning technologies to analyse electronic health record data and predict high risk individuals towards pancreatic cancer for early-stage management of the disease.

The actors interacting with the iHelp platform, identified in D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21) and described in detail in D2.4 (Mel 21), are:

- **Health Care Professional (HCP):** the physicians taking care of the citizens' health and risk of developing the Pancreatic Cancer
- **Individual/Patient:** the citizen/patient enrolled in the iHelp project that will use its functionalities
- **Model Builder:** the data scientist in charge of training the models for better tuning the AI algorithms
- **External Sources:** other external system, such as: laboratory systems (LS), social networks, databases, etc.

2.1 Architecture

The reference architecture of the iHelp platform has been driven by the user and technical (system and software) requirements elicited in D2.1. The iHelp components implementing the requirements have been identified and described in deliverable D2.4. The architecture of the platform is shown in Figure 1, where four big blocks are visible:

- The **Data Storage** manages the persistence of the data used in the iHelp platform.
- The **Final user applications** are the apps dedicated to the human actors of the system (i.e. **HCP**, **Individual** and **ModelBuilder**). Their user interfaces will be described in deliverable D2.8 – User Centric Design I.
- The **Data Ingestion** includes the components processing primary and secondary data and storing them in the **Data Storage**.

- The **Data Analysis** abstracts from the AI components elaborating the data saved in the **Data Storage** to feed the **Final User Application**.

Figure 1: iHelp Architecture (Mel 21).

At this point, it should be noted that components depicted in grey will be available subsequently and fully described in the next release of these specifications deliverable D2.7 during M20.

The hexagon shape denotes the micro-services that communicate asynchronously, using a message broker (see section 2.1.2), while rectangles represent the components that offer or use an API for asynchronous communication. The type of interfaces used or provided is reported in the attached label, e.g. REST API.

The goals and main interactions of the iHelp components are delineated in D2.4. (Mel 21).

2.1.1 Internal components

As a result of the incremental approach adopted in the project for the development, the present specification focuses on the subset of components and services that are more mature according to the project schedule and the actual progresses, highlighted in Figure 1, while other components expected for next periods according to the project roadmap (the grey transparent ones in Figure 1) will be defined in more detail in the next development cycle.

Specifically, the following list includes the existing components, whose external interfaces are documented in the present document, also referencing for each of them the documents where their detailed design are reported:

- Data Connectors (D3.3 (K., M., P. + 21) and D3.5 (P., S., P. + 21))
- Data Gateway (D3.3)
- Data Cleaner (D3.7 (M., W., D. + 21))
- Data Qualifier (D3.7)
- Data Harmoniser (D3.7)
- HHR Importer (D3.3, D4.9)
- Secondary Data Pre-processor (D3.5)
- Personalised Predictor (D4.1)
- Analytics Workbench - Model Library (D4.4)
- Social Analyser (D5.8)
- Monitoring and Alerting (D5.4)
- Big Data Platform (D4.9)

2.1.2 Components off-the-shelf

The following off-the-shelf components, already available from a commercial source or as open-source software, are part of the iHelp architecture:

- Apache Kafka¹ is an event streaming platform ensuring a continuous flow and interpretation of data. It allows to:
 - capture data in real-time from event sources like databases, sensors, mobile devices, cloud services, and software applications in the form of streams of events
 - store event streams
 - manipulate, process, and react to the event streams both in real-time and retrospectively
 - route the event streams to different destination technologies as needed. Event streaming thus ensures a continuous flow and interpretation of data so that the right information is at the right place, at the right time.

It is available for all iHelp components, but specifically used for the asynchronous communication of the data ingestion components.

- Keycloak² is an open-source Identity and Access Management tool permitting to add authentication to applications and secure services. In the context of iHelp this solution is adopted to allow access only to authorised users. iHelp can be configured to support OpenID Connect (OIDC)³, an identity layer on top of the OAuth 2.0 protocol that makes also an extensive use of the Json Web Token (JWT) set of standards.
- Traefik⁴ enables routing client API requests to backend microservices and provides key capabilities such as API security, traffic management, and observability. In the iHelp reference architecture it is labelled as API Gateway and will dispatch the external invocation to specific internal services.

¹ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

² <https://www.keycloak.org/>

³ <https://openid.net/connect/>

⁴ <https://traefik.io/solutions/api-gateway/>

- Kubernetes⁵ is a portable, extensible, open-source platform for managing containerized workloads and services, that facilitates both declarative configuration and automation. In iHelp solution this will be useful as orchestrator for the deploy of all the containerised components.

⁵ <https://kubernetes.io/>

3 Functional Specification

This section is intended to describe the iHelp platform behaviour, by outlining how the requirements collected in D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21) will be addressed by the components being part of the iHelp architecture.

It is intended to be a reference for technical partners and support for development teams to understand components' functions and how to interact with them.

These specifications can also help stakeholders to understand whether their requirements have been properly taken into account when designing the architecture and the functionalities of the iHelp components.

3.1 API documentation

This section focuses on the programming interfaces that the iHelp components currently available will provide to interact each other. The APIs reported in this documentation will be extended or enhanced in the next release of the deliverable, as the knowledge on components evolves.

Components are here seen as black boxes: functions intended for internal use and implementation details are out of the scope of the present document and will be reported in the related WP deliverables (see section 2.1.1).

The template used to collect the API documentation, reported below, allows to specify three types of components:

- components communicating asynchronously via a message broker.
- components offering REST APIs.
- components providing other interfaces, such as JDBC.

The template is structured as follows:

Component name

The component goals and functions are briefly described here.

Depending on the type of component (according to the above list), one of the following subsection is filled:

1. Asynchronous communication:

Specifies if the component is Consumer or Producer and the related topic(s).

2. REST API:

In case the component exposes a REST API, following information is requested.

BASE URL: */myinterface*

The base URL is the entry point to invoke the exposed service.

For each method provided by the exposed service, following details are reported.

- Method Name: the name of the method the following tables are referring to.

Purpose of the method

In this section is provided the main purpose of the method, which could be its goal and main process that will be performed internally.

Request

This section describes the right way to invoke the service by documenting the Request message that should be generated by the client of this API.

In the Method column will be reported the kind of the method published (i.e. GET/PUT/POST/DELETE), and in the URL column the full URL needed for invoking the service (e.g. /helloworld). This URL concatenates with the Base URL to form the full path (e.g. /myinterface/helloworld).

Table 1: REST API documentation – Request URL

Method	URL
[KIND_OF_METHOD]	

The parameters required from the service are detailed in the following table. In the TYPE column will be stated the kind of parameter (e.g. in the header/body of the request or if the parameter is present in the path. For instance, if the path is /helloworld/{nickname} the parameter “nickname” should be detailed in the following table. The Params column is reserved to the name of the parameter, following the previous example “nickname”. In the Values column will be reported the value type for the specific param (e.g. String), or the enumeration description if the param has to be one of enumerated value. The Description column is dedicated to a high level description in order to better clarify the meaning of the parameter.

Table 2: REST API documentation – Request parameters

TYPE	Params	Values (#)	Description
Head	A	String	
body	B	String	
Path	C	<i>Patient primary data</i>	

Response

In the Response section, if already known, will be described the possible response for the specific service, both successful and error invocation.

The status code column is reserved for collecting the possible response status code. The Response column instead will contain a structure of a possible response related to those Status codes, or, if not known at the moment, a high-level description of a possible response.

Table 3: REST API documentation – Response

Status code	Response
200	{ THE CORRECT RETURNED OBJECT/RESPONSE STRUCTURE }
403	{"error": "A is missing."}
...	...
500	{"error": "Something went wrong. Please try again later."}

3. Other components

Specifies the interfaces provided by the component and how to interact with it.

For readability reasons, the complete API documentation is reported in Annex A.

3.2 Use cases

In D2.1, the five pilots describe their purpose and the expected usage of the iHelp platform from a use case perspective, including UML diagrams, and identify the needs that the architecture should comply with by presenting the initial list of user requirements.

The list of use cases, initially circulated in D2.1 and then refined in D2.4 (Mel 21) has been used to drive the description of iHelp components interaction in section 3.3.

Table 4: iHelp Use cases

Use case	Actor(s)	Pilots
Advice follow-up	Health Care Professional Individual	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU
Advice review	Health Care Professional Individual	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU
Caption of profiling characteristics	Health Care Professional Individual	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU
Communication of risk	iHelp AI Individual	TMU
Data visualization	Health Care Professional	FPG, TMU
Develop risk prediction model	Model Builder	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU
Elevated risk detected	Health Care Professional	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU
Ingest tests and samples results	External Source (Lab System)	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU
Monitoring	Health Care Professional Individual	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU
Plan visit/control	Health Care Professional	FPG
Request tests and samples	Health Care Professional	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU
Risk assessment	Health Care Professional	UNIMAN, HDM, MUP, TMU
Risk mitigation delivery	Health Care Professional Individual Model Builder	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU
Risk mitigation/treatment planning	Health Care Professional Individual	UNIMAN, FPG, HDM, MUP, TMU

Use case	Actor(s)	Pilots
	External Source (Lab System)	

3.3 iHelp components interactions

Activity diagrams are used to describe the dynamic behaviour of the iHelp platform and the interaction among iHelp components in this deliverable. In this phase of the project, due to the incremental approach in the development, information on the exchange of messages among components is still not sufficient to design sequence diagrams, that will be included in the next version of this deliverable.

The activity diagrams illustrating how the different components interact to carry out the functions described by use cases in section 3.2, and the order in which such an interaction occur, are reported in the following sections.

3.3.1 Advice follow-up

The activity diagram shown in Figure 2 represents the course of actions to be executed during the follow-up of the risk mitigation advice directed to high-risk of developing PC subjects. Once the patient is evaluated at risk and a risk mitigation is delivered (see section 3.3.15), the clinician initiates a follow-up of the same during which iHelp platform shares with the clinician patient's lifestyle information, gathered through monitoring (see section 3.3.11), and further elaboration and integrates the current clinical information. Using the web application, the clinician can analyse the effect of the sent messages on the patient's behaviour to estimate and evaluate which is the best pattern of intervention for the specific patient.

The involved iHelp components are the Web app for HCP and the Big Data Platform.

Figure 2: Advice follow-up activity diagram.

The process is started by the Health Care Professional in charge of treating patients undergoing risk mitigation. The professional chooses to view the list of his/her patients in the Web App, that retrieves it from the Big Data Platform. The Health Care Professional selects a patient from the list visualised in the

Web app to view his/her current available data. The Web App queries the Big Data Platform to retrieve primary data, secondary data and the messages exchanged between the patient and the professional, and then visualises a report showing all obtained data.

3.3.2 Advice review

The activity diagram shown in Figure 3 represents the sequence of actions to be performed in case of advice review during the risk mitigation for high-risk of developing PC subjects. Abnormal values detected when monitoring (see section 3.3.11) patients already undergoing risk mitigation are reported to the clinician, that should contact the patient and take action.

The involved iHelp components are the Web app for HCP, The Personalised Advisor and the Big Data Platform.

The process is started by the Health Care Professional treating the patient whose abnormalities are discovered. The Health Care Professional accesses the Web App and selects the communication section, where a list of personalised messages (specific to nature of risks associated with the patient), needing his/her acceptance, is visualised. The clinician is asked to approve or reject them via the Web App. In the latter situation the process terminates. If the Health Care Professional approves the messages, the Personalised Advisor first forwards them to the patient and then stores them in the Big Data Platform.

Figure 3: Advice review activity diagram.

3.3.3 Caption of profiling characteristics

The activity diagram displayed in Figure 4 describes the course of actions to be performed during profiling of individuals that be involved in the pilots and will use the Mobile app, with the objective of capture the characteristics of these individuals.

The only iHelp component involved in this process is the Mobile app.

The process is started by the individual taking part in the pilot. When the individual accesses the Mobile app for the first time, he/she is prompted to fill in a pre-defined questionnaire. The individual completes the questionnaire and enters the requested information, that is then inserted in the system following the Secondary data Ingestion process (see section 3.3.10).

Figure 4: Caption of profiling characteristics activity diagram.

3.3.4 Communication of risk

The activity diagram depicted in Figure 5 models the activities carried out to communicate the estimated high level of risk of contracting PC to the individual participating in the pilot. The risk level is estimated following the process designed in the Risk assessment activity diagram (see section 3.3.14).

The involved iHelp components are the Web app for HCP, The Personalised Advisor and the Big Data Platform.

The process is started by the Personalised Advisor on request coming by the Health Care professional via the Web App (see section 3.3.7) that communicates the estimated high risk to the patient and then notifies the Web App that visualises a report including the information sent to the patient and then invokes the Big Data Platform to store the related data.

Figure 5: Communication of risk activity diagram.

3.3.5 Data visualization

The following activity diagram (see Figure 6) identifies the course of actions performed to let the clinician analyse collected patient data. The iHelp platform shares with the clinician patient's lifestyle information, gathered through monitoring (see section 3.3.11), and further elaboration and integrates the current clinical information, so that the Health Care Professional can decide whether further action, such as an advice (see section 3.3.2), or the need for a visit (see section 3.3.12), is required.

The only iHelp component involved in this process is the DSS Dashboard.

The process is initiated by the Health Care Professional that accesses the DSS Dashboard related to his/her patient by entering patient id. The DSS Dashboard retrieves patient data, both primary and secondary, and visualises them in a report.

Figure 6: Data visualization activity diagram.

3.3.6 Develop risk prediction model

Figure 7 depicts the preliminary activity diagram defining the sequence of actions to carry out to train a risk prediction model with genomics and epidemiological data and use it to assess a participant’s risk.

The involved iHelp components are the Analytic Workbench and the Big Data Platform.

The process is initiated by the Model Builder that invokes the Analytic Workbench to retrieve data from the Big Data Platform. Once data is provided and shown, the Model Builder edits the model and stores it.

Figure 7: Develop risk prediction model activity diagram.

3.3.7 Elevated risk detected

The activity diagram shown in Figure 8 represents the course of actions to be performed when the estimation of the risk of developing Pancreatic Cancer (defined in the diagram in section Figure 19), required by the Health Care Professional via the Web application, returns a high value.

The involved iHelp components are the Web app for HCP, the Predictor & Risk Identifier and the Personalised Advisor.

The process is started by the Predictor & Risk Identifier that, when computes a high risk for a patient returns, in addition to the estimated risk level, an explanation of why the risk was evaluated as high. This clarification is visualised in the Web, which prompts the Health Care Professional to confirm or reject the risk level estimate. In case of confirmation, the Health Care Professional can order additional samples and laboratory tests via the Web app (see Request Test and Samples in section 3.3.13) and then is asked to choose in the Web app whether to notify the patient of the elevated risk. The eventual request to communicate the high risk to the patient is then sent to the Personalised Advisor (see Communication of risk in section 3.3.4).

Figure 8: Elevated risk detected activity diagram.

3.3.8 Ingest tests and samples results

The activity diagrams reported in this section describe the activities to be performed to ingest data in the iHelp platform. The data ingestion pipeline processes and stores data derived from different sources, also external to the iHelp project, both historic (primary) data of Cancer patients and (secondary) data gathered through the mobile and wearable applications. The process of ingesting test and samples in the system is a particular case of primary data ingestion.

Primary and secondary data ingestion have been modelled in different activity diagrams. To avoid complex diagrams the whole activity diagrams have been split. The Kafka Message Bus has not been included in these diagrams, that model only dispatching and reception of messages with specific topics

3.3.9 Primary data ingestion

The first step of the primary data ingestion pipeline is described in Figure 9 and involves the Primary Data Connector and the Data Gateway, in addition to external components such as FTP server and JDBC DB making primary data available.

The first step of data ingestion is started by the Primary Data Connector that retrieves data from primary data sources. Different types of data connectors provide different means for connectivity. At this phase of the project, two types of primary data connectors are foreseen: the FTP Connector gets data stored in static files in an FTP server while the JDBC Connector executes a query statement in a JDBC compatible database. Hence, currently two types of primary data sources have been considered in iHelp: FTP servers and JDBC databases. In the first case the FTP Connector is invoked to return static files from the server. In the second case, the JDBC Connector interacts with a database, that returns the results of the queries executed by the connector. All primary data connectors return generic byte buffers that are sent to the

Data Gateway via a REST API. The Data Gateway first checks the security keys enclosed in the message received by the Data Connector against the ones defined for a specific connector. If the message is not authorized the process is terminated, otherwise the message is transformed in the appropriate format and sent to the Message Bus with topic T1, to be consumed by the Data Cleaner (see Figure 10).

Figure 9: Primary data ingestion - step 1 activity diagram.

The second step of the primary data ingestion pipeline is described in Figure 10 and involves only the Data Cleaner, that starts the process taking as input the message shared in the Message Bus Kafka with topic T1. Then the Data Cleaner validates received data by identifying errors based on conformance to a specific set of constraints, cleans data by correcting or removing elements for which validation errors were previously raised and verifies data by ensuring that all the corrective actions performed by data cleaning have been executed in compliance with the data models design of the iHelp platform and that datasets are error free. Data resulting from this process is finally sent to the Message Bus with topic T2, to be consumed by the Data Qualifier (see next step of primary data ingestion in Figure 11).

Figure 10: Primary data ingestion - step 2 activity diagram.

The third step of the primary data ingestion pipeline is described in Figure 11 and involves only the Data Qualifier, that starts the process taking as input the message shared in the Message Bus Kafka with topic T2. Then the Data Qualifier retrieves data quality by categorizing received data according to specific levels of trustworthiness, including data reliability, provided data type, data source availability. If level of trustworthiness is acceptable, i.e. greater or equal a predefined threshold, data is sent to the Message Bus with topic T3, to be consumed by the Data Harmoniser (see next step of primary data ingestion in Figure 12), otherwise the process is terminated.

Figure 11: Primary data ingestion - step 3 activity diagram.

The fourth step of the primary data ingestion pipeline is described in Figure 12 and involves only the Data Harmoniser, that starts the process taking as input the message shared in the Message Bus Kafka with topic T3. The Data Harmoniser automatically translates acquired data from different languages, harmonises it and then annotates it with appropriate metadata. Resulting data is then handled by the Primary Mapper subcomponent that maps primary data into HHR, by providing the transformation functions required to map the primary data to the holistic health records stored in the iHelp platform, and finally sends it to the Message Bus with topic T4, to be consumed by the HHR Importer (see final step of primary data ingestion in Figure 13).

Figure 12: Primary data ingestion - step 4 activity diagram.

The fifth and final step of the primary data ingestion pipeline is described in Figure 13 and involves the HHR Importer and the Big Data Platform. The HHR Importer starts the process taking as input the message shared in the Message Bus Kafka with topic T4 and preparing it for storage, by transforming the HHR entities into data items that will be stored into data tables of the Big Data Platform. Afterwards the HHR Importer connects to and sends processed primary data to the Big Data Platform that finally stores it and terminates the primary data pipeline.

Figure 13: Final step of primary data ingestion activity diagram.

3.3.10 Secondary data ingestion

The first step of the second data ingestion pipeline is described in Figure 14 and involves the Mobile App, the Secondary Data Pre-Processor, the Secondary Data Connector and the Data Gateway, in addition to external services providing secondary data.

The first step of secondary data ingestion is started by the Mobile App by pushing available data to the Secondary Data Pre-Processor, that also recurrently retrieves data from device manufactures' servers (external services) and processes received data. The Secondary Data Connector periodically sends requests for secondary data to the Secondary Data Pre-processor, that provides them. Data received from the Secondary Data Pre-processor are then forwarded by the Data Connector to the Data Gateway via a REST API. The Data Gateway first checks the security keys enclosed in the message received by the Data Connector against the ones defined for a specific connector. If the message is not authorized the process is terminated, otherwise the message is transformed in the appropriate format and sent to the Message Bus with topic T1, to be consumed by the Data Cleaner. The second and third steps of the secondary data ingestion pipeline, involving the Data Cleaner and the Data Qualifier are equal to the respective steps of primary data ingestion (modelled respectively in Figure 10 and Figure 11), therefore are not explained here again.

Figure 14: Secondary data ingestion - step 1 activity diagram.

At the end of the third step of secondary ingestion, the Data Qualifier sends trustworthy data to the Message Bus with topic T3, to be consumed by the Data Harmoniser (see fourth step of secondary data ingestion in Figure 15).

Figure 15: Secondary data ingestion - step 4 activity diagram.

The fourth step of the secondary data ingestion pipeline is described in Figure 15 and involves only the Data Harmoniser. Same as done in the respective primary data ingestion step, the Data Harmoniser starts the process taking as input the message shared in the Message Bus Kafka with topic T3, automatically translates it from different languages, harmonises it and then annotates it with appropriate metadata. In this case resulting data is handled by the Secondary Mapper subcomponent that maps secondary data into HHR and finally sends it to the Message Bus with topic T4, to be consumed by the HHR Importer, that prepares data for storing processed secondary data in the Big Data Platform (in the same way as occurred in the final step of the primary data ingestion pipeline modelled in Figure 13).

3.3.11 Monitoring

The activity diagram shown in Figure 16 describes the course of actions to be performed to monitor high-risk subjects for early identification of warning signs. Constant monitoring, by checking and aggregating

data coming from secondary data sources (mobile and or wearable devices) and comparing them with personalized targets issued by the medical experts, allows the Health Care Professional to follow-up (see section) a patient estimated at high risk of contracting PC. The system continuously adds new data to the previous stored and reassess the health risk of the controlled patient.

The involved iHelp components are the Monitoring and Alerting and the Big Data Platform.

The Monitoring and Alerting component periodically retrieves patient secondary data by querying the Big Data Platform, that provides it so that the Monitoring and Alerting can analyse it and take appropriate action through risk mitigation (see section 3.3.2).

Figure 16: Monitoring activity diagram.

3.3.12 Plan visit/control

The activity diagram displayed in Figure 17 identifies the actions to be performed to plan a visit/control. During the follow-up of the risk mitigation advice directed to high-risk of developing PC patients, according to the patient info shared by the system (see section 3.3.5), the clinician can determine the need for a visit.

The involved iHelp components are the Web App for HCP, the Personalised Advisor and the Big Data Platform.

Figure 17: Plan a visit or control activity diagram.

The process is started by the Health Care Professional that accesses the communication section of the Web App, where a list of possible messages for the patient is visualised. The Health Care Professional selects from the list the appropriate message and the Web App forwards the message to the Personalised Advisor that delivers it to the patient. The notification of successful delivery is then visualised in the Web App and stored in the Big Data Platform.

3.3.13 Request tests and samples

The diagram displayed in Figure 1: iHelp Architecture identifies the actions carried out to request a patient to execute a set of laboratory tests, on request of the Health Care Professional via the Web application. This event occurs after a high risk of contracting PC is estimated, in order to have a more precise risk assessment.

The involved iHelp components are the Web app for HCP and the Mobile app.

The process is started by the Health Care Professional, that accesses the Web app section allowing to request tests. The Web app checks whether a default list of tests has been defined; if not the process terminates, otherwise the Web app verifies if the default test set needs to be approved by the Health Care professional. If no approval is required, a report including all the tests/samples to be provided is visualised in the Web app. If the professional acceptance is demanded, the proposed list of tests/samples is viewed in the Web app and the Health Care Professional is prompted to accept or reject it. In event of rejection, the process terminates. In case of approval, the Health Profession can directly accept the proposed list or can decide to modify it by selecting the “Edit test” function of the Web app and is then asked again to approve the modified list. When the list of tests is finally confirmed, a report including all the tests/samples is visualised in the Web app and the related execution request is notified to the patient via the Mobile app. After the patient undergoes the tests in the Clinical Analysis Laboratory, the laboratory generates the test results and inserts them in the iHelp platform with the data ingestion process.

Figure 18: Request tests and samples activity diagrams.

3.3.14 Risk assessment

The diagram shown in Figure 19 describes the activities performed to estimate the individual risk of developing PC, on request of the Health Care Professional via the Web application.

The involved iHelp components are the Web app for HCP, the Big Data Platform and the Predictor & Risk Identifier.

Figure 19: Risk assessment activity diagrams.

The process is started by the Health Care Professional that enters the patient id in the Web app, by selecting it from the list of the identifiers of his/her patients, to access the patient dashboard, where it is possible to request the patient’s risk estimation. The Web app forwards the risk estimation request to the Predictor & Risk Identifier, that first of all retrieve patient’s data from the Big Data Platform. If data cannot be found, an error is sent to the Web app, that notifies a warning on the dashboard and prompts the Health Care Professional to insert additional information. If patient’s data is available, the Predictor & Risk Identifier extracts required info from HHR; if additional details are needed, a request is sent to the Web app, that notifies a warning on the dashboard and prompts the Health Care Professional to insert

them. If data is not available the process is ended, otherwise the Health Care Professional enters the required info in the Web app, that forwards it to the Predictor & Risk Identifier. Once the Predictor & Risk Identifier has all required data, it computes patient's risk and returns the estimated level to the Web app, that visualises it on the patient's dashboard. The risk factor is classified as low, medium or high. In case the resulting risk is regarded as high, a dedicated process is started (see Elevated risk detected in section 3.3.7).

3.3.15 Risk mitigation delivery

The diagram shown in Figure 20: *Risk mitigation delivery* activity diagram identifies the course of actions carried out to deliver a risk mitigation advice after an assessment of a high level of risk of developing PC for a patient. A treatment plan is first proposed to the Health Care Professional and, if approved, is submitted to the patient.

The involved iHelp components are the Monitoring and Alerting, the Big Data Platform and the Personalised Advisor.

The Monitoring and Alerting component periodically retrieves treatment plan and checks whether Health Care Professional approval is required. If yes, the plan is stored in the Big Data Platform as needing approval. If not, the treatment plan is forwarded to the Personalised Advisor that communicates it to the patient and then stores the communication in the Big Data Platform.

Figure 20: Risk mitigation delivery activity diagram.

3.3.16 Risk mitigation/treatment planning

The diagram depicted in Figure 21 describes the course of actions carried out to plan a risk mitigation advice or a treatment for a patient estimated at high risk of contracting PC (or already diagnosed with PC and undergoing treatment). Once laboratory tests of a patient, requested by the Health Care Professional (see section 3.3.13) after a high risk estimate (see section 3.3.7), have been processed and primary data and questionnaires info are acquired, the risk mitigation planning is started.

The involved iHelp components are the Web App for HCP, the DSS Dashboard and the Monitoring and Alerting.

The process is started by the Web App, that visualises a list of all patients of a clinician directed to risk mitigation advice so that the Health Care Professional can select one of them, view his/her information and determine whether further details are needed. If yes, the Health Care Professional accesses the DSS

Dashboard to retrieve required information (see Data Visualization at section 3.3.5). Otherwise, the clinician should confirm that a treatment planning is necessary. If not, the process terminates. If yes, the Health Care Professional selects the suitable plan for the patient from a list of proposed plans visualised in the Web App. The chosen intervention plan is then forwarded to the Monitoring and Alerting component, that sets the rules for the specific patient and plan.

Figure 21: Risk mitigation/treatment planning activity diagram.

3.4 Traceability matrix

The following figure and tables show the involvement of the iHelp components in the different use cases. This section details better which module of each component is impacted by the use case in order to satisfy the behaviour modelled in the activity diagrams.

				Develop Risk Prediction Model Risk Assessment	Request Tests and Samples	Elevated Risk Detected	Inject Tests and Samples results	Risk Mitigation/Treatment planning	Advice Review	Risk Mitigation Delivery	Monitoring	Advice Follow-up	Caption of profiling characteristics	Plan a visit or control	Data Visualisation	Communication of risk
Data Connector	/connector	POST	/				?				?					
Data Gateway	/gateway	POST	/data_gateway				?				?					
Data Gateway		Produce	T1				x				x					
Data Cleaner		Consume	T1				x				x					
Data Cleaner		Produce	T2				x				x					
Data Qualifier		Consume	T2				x				x					
Data Qualifier		Produce	T3				x				x					
Data Harmoniser		Consume	T3				x				x					
Data Harmoniser		Produce	T4				x									
Data Harmoniser		Produce	T5								x					
HHR Importer		Consume	T4				x									
HHR Importer		Consume	T5								x					
Big Data Platform		CREATE		?			x		?	x	x			x		x
Big Data Platform		READ		x	x	?		x	x			x			x	
Big Data Platform		UPDATE		?												
Big Data Platform		DELETE		?												
Secondary Data Pre-Processor	/1.2/health-api/	GET	/patients/{id}/physical-data/{pat1}/date/{referenceDate}								x					
Secondary Data Pre-Processor	/1.2/health-api/	GET	/patients/{id}/physical-data/{pat2}/date/{referenceDate}								x					
Secondary Data Pre-Processor	/1.2/health-api/	GET	/patients/physiology-data								x					
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD			x	x		?	x	x			x		x
Analytic Workbench	/	GET	/api/model/	x										x		
Analytic Workbench	/	POST	/api/app/rules/{modelid}	?												
Analytic Workbench	/	GET	/api/app/rules/{modelid}	?												
Social Analyser	/	GET	/api/alerts	?												
Predictor&Risk Identifier	TBD	TBD	TBD	?	?		?									
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/risk		x		x									
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/survival		x		x									
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/factors		x		x									
DSS Dashboard	GUI			?				?				?			x	
WebApp for HCP	GUI				x	x	x	x	x			x		x		x
Mobile App	GUI					x							x			
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/alertrule?status={status}					?								
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/alertrule/{id}					?								
Monitoring and Alerting	/	POST	/alertrule					?								
Monitoring and Alerting	/	PUT	/alertrule/{id}					?								
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/evaluate/rule/{id}							?	x					
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/evaluate/patient/{patientid}/rule/{ruleid}									?				
Monitoring and Alerting	/	POST	/send/alerts							x						
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/alerts/patient/{id}										?			
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/history?type={name}								x		?			
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/history/patient/{id}								x		?			
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/motivationaladvice/patient/{patientid}/rules/{ruleid}									x				

Figure 22: Use Case/Methods Matrix.

In the following tables, are listed, for every Use Case, which method is involved.

Table 5: Components' methods involved in the *Develop Risk Prediction Model* Use Case

Develop Risk Prediction Model*			
Component	Base URL	Type	Signature or Topic
Big Data Platform			CREATE
Big Data Platform			READ

Develop Risk Prediction Model*			
Big Data Platform			UPDATE
Big Data Platform			DELETE
Analytic Workbench	/	GET	/api/model/
Analytic Workbench	/	POST	/api/app/rules/{modelId}
Analytic Workbench	/	GET	/api/app/rules/{modelId}
Social Analyser	/	GET	/api/alerts
Predictor&Risk Identifier	TBD	TBD	TBD
DSS Dashboard	GUI		

Table 6: Components' methods involved in the *Risk Assessment* Use Case

Risk Assessment			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			READ
Predictor&Risk Identifier	TBD	TBD	TBD
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/risk
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/survival
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/factors
WebApp for HCP	GUI		

Table 7: Components' methods involved in the *Request Tests and Samples* Use Case

Request Tests and Samples			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			READ
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD
WebApp for HCP	GUI		
Mobile App	GUI		

Table 8: Components' methods involved in the *Elevated Risk Detected* Use Case

Elevated Risk Detected			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD
Predictor&Risk Identifier	TBD	TBD	TBD
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/risk

Elevated Risk Detected			
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/survival
Personalised Predictor	/	POST	/factors
WebApp for HCP	GUI		

Table 9: Components' methods involved in the *Ingest Tests and Samples results* Use Case

Ingest Tests and Samples results			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Data Connector	/connector	POST	/
Data Gateway	/gateway	POST	/data_gateway
Data Gateway		Produce	T1
Data Cleaner		Consume	T1
Data Cleaner		Produce	T2
Data Qualifier		Consume	T2
Data Qualifier		Produce	T3
Data Harmoniser		Consume	T3
Data Harmoniser		Produce	T4
HHR Importer		Consume	T4
Big Data Platform			CREATE

Table 10: Components' methods involved in the *Risk Mitigation/Treatment planning* Use Case

Risk Mitigation/Treatment planning			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			READ
DSS Dashboard	GUI		
WebApp for HCP	GUI		

Table 11: Components' methods involved in the *Advice Review* Use Case

Advice Review			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			CREATE
Big Data Platform			READ
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD
WebApp for HCP	GUI		

Table 12: Components' methods involved in the *Risk Mitigation Delivery* Use Case

Risk Mitigation Delivery			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			CREATE
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/evaluate/rule/{id}
Monitoring and Alerting	/	POST	/send/alerts

Table 13: Components' methods involved in the *Monitoring* Use Case

Monitoring			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Data Connector	/connector	POST	/
Data Gateway	/gateway	POST	/data_gateway
Data Gateway		Produce	T1
Data Cleaner		Consume	T1
Data Cleaner		Produce	T2
Data Qualifier		Consume	T2
Data Qualifier		Produce	T3
Data Harmoniser		Consume	T3
Data Harmoniser		Produce	T5
HHR Importer		Consume	T5
Big Data Platform			CREATE
Secondary Data Pre-Processor	/1.2/health-api/	GET	/patients/{id}/physical-data/pat1/date/{referenceDate}
Secondary Data Pre-Processor	/1.2/health-api/	GET	/patients/{id}/physical-data/pat2/date/{referenceDate}
Secondary Data Pre-Processor	/1.2/health-api/	GET	/patients/physiology-data
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/evaluate/rule/{id}
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/history/type/{name}
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/history/patient/{id}

Table 14: Components' methods involved in the *Advice Follow-up* Use Case

Advice Follow-up			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			READ

Advice Follow-up			
DSS Dashboard	GUI		
WebApp for HCP	GUI		
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/evaluate/patient/{patientId}/rule/{ruleId}
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/alerts/patient/{id}
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/history/type/{name}
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/history/patient/{id}
Monitoring and Alerting	/	GET	/motivationaladvice/patient/{patientId}/rules/{ruleId}

Table 15: Components' methods involved in the *Caption of profiling characteristics* Use Case

Caption of profiling characteristics			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Mobile App	GUI		

Table 16: Components' methods involved in the *Plan a visit or control* Use Case

Plan a visit or control			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			CREATE
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD
WebApp for HCP	GUI		

Table 17: Components' methods involved in the *Data Visualisation* Use Case

Data Visualisation			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			READ
DSS Dashboard	GUI		

Table 18: Components' methods involved in the *Communication of risk* Use Case

Communication of risk			
<i>Component</i>	<i>Base URL</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Signature or Topic</i>
Big Data Platform			CREATE
PersonalisedAdvisor	TBD	TBD	TBD
WebApp for HCP	GUI		

4 Non-Functional specifications

In this section are available the non-functional specification useful to address the non-functional requirements emerged in the D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21). The reference code of those requirements is stated in squared brackets in the text.

4.1 Security & Privacy

The data providers partners will sign an agreement in which is clearly stated the roles of the different actors, in terms of Data Controller and Data Processor following the GDPR definition (see requirement [T-REQ-T3.3-12] in D2.1).

Furthermore, the data that will be provided as input will be anonymised at the source. The system will refer internally the patient with a unique id. In the case of a mobile application related to the same patient, that linkage will be maintained internally in the iHelp platform.

All the external requests must be authorised from the internal Identity Manager (IM) (i.e. keycloak, introduced in section 2.1.2). Only the authorised users and applications can use the iHelp API. The IM must be configured with a robust mechanism of password reset/restore and a role-based authorisation mechanism.

4.2 Scalability

The solution must support multiple data streaming in input, specifically the Data Ingestion pipeline (see requirement [T-REQ-T3.1-02] in D2.1). Taking advantage of the asynchronous communication and dynamic nature of that part of the system it will be possible to instantiate dynamically more component if needed.

The component that will implement the message bus (i.e. Kafka, described in section 2.1.2), will be configured to allow multiple contemporary pipeline of data ingestion (see requirement [T-REQ-T3.1-03] in D2.1).

4.3 Maintainability

The managing of the virtual machine and the hardware provided for the final deploy will carried out by the actual provider. Every component leader needs the grant to access the virtual machine to configure, install, maintain or analyse his own component.

The components should be internally designed for easing the updates and the bug fixing procedures (e.g. using SSH connection, management dashboard, custom webpage, etc.).

All the developed software will be available as containerised components, in order to ease the deploy and the upscaling of the solution. The components will be managed by the Kubernetes orchestrator, and its dynamic deploy will speed up the manual procedures (see requirement [T-REQ-T3.2-01] in D2.1). Furthermore, using the orchestrator API the administrator will be able to describe the definition of services to permit the automatic instantiation and deploy for the different deployment scenarios (see requirement [T-REQ-T3.2-03] in D2.1).

In the further cycle of the incremental process, will be analysed also the possibility to have a GUI for letting the data provider configure the pipeline for data ingestion directly from his dashboard (see requirement [T-REQ-T3.2-04] in D2.1).

4.4 Reliability

The internal storage of the platform will be able to keep the data in three as linked ontologies, allowing the storage of the semantic facts and the corresponding data schema model. If those data are produced and consumed by the same component, is also possible to store those internally, in order to not overload the BigDataPlatform used from the whole solution (see requirement [T-REQ-T3.4-17] in D2.1).

The BigDataPlatform will guaranteed a stable connection towards the other components, allowing the connection from a pool of client (see requirement [T-REQ-T4.4-02] in D2.1). Furthermore, it will be designed to respect the ACID properties for the databases, in order to allow the upscaling of the solution, if in the case of [T-REQ-T4.4-02] (see the related requirement in D2.1).

4.5 Other

The web application designed for Health Care Professionals and Model Builders will be usable through a modern web browser, such as:

- Google Chrome (v80+)
- Safari (13+)
- Firefox (v72+)
- Edge (80+)

The mobile application for individuals and patients will be usable through a smartphone:

- Android (v6+)
- iOS (v10+)

The specification about the usability, user experience, look&feel and other user-related topics will be addressed in the T2.4 - User Centred Design and detailed in the D2.8 - User Centric Design I.

5 Conclusions and future work

In this deliverable we reported the initial functional and non-functional specifications of the iHelp platform, aimed at specifying the interfaces between the iHelp components currently under development and delegating details on components' internal functions and processing to the respective deliverables.

Specifically, in Annex A we have documented 70 APIs related to components providing REST interfaces, detail how components communicating asynchronously interact via the message broker and how to access to the central data repository. All these components are described in deliverable D2.4 (Mel 21) and satisfy the requirements currently identify and collected in deliverable D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21).

Additionally, we presented twenty activity diagrams aim at specifying how the components interact to carry out the functions described by the fourteen use cases' scenarios introduced in D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21) and refined in D2.4 (Mel 21), and the order in which these interactions happen. We have also produced a traceability matrix better detailing which module of each component is impacted by which use case scenario, in order to satisfy the behaviours modelled in the activity diagrams.

The non-functional specifications that the overall iHelp platform aims at meeting the non-functional requirements reported in D2.1 (M., M., P. + 21) have been also provided.

Our work has focussed on the information available on the iHelp platform and its components at the moment. Due to the incremental development approach adopted in the project, several components, although foreseen in the iHelp architecture, will be designed and implemented after the release of this document and therefore object of forthcoming work; at the moment data ingestion components, developed within WP3, are at higher maturity level than data consumption components (WP4 and WP5), for which work to date has just started according to the project roadmap.

In the next version of this deliverable, D2.7 – Functional and Non-Functional Specifications II expected at M20, the specifications of the whole iHelp platform will be provided, by completing the specifications related to the components that are currently at an early stage, such as those belonging to the Data Analysis block, that elaborates data stored in the central repository, previously ingested by WP3 components. Furthermore, thanks to a more detailed knowledge of the components, we will enhance the functional specifications by providing the Swagger/Open API documentation and Kafka topics, details on message serialization and sequence diagrams including also message exchange among components. Also, new and updated requirements coming from D2.2 – State of the art and requirements analysis II and the final release of the iHelp architecture in D2.5 – Conceptual model and reference architecture II will be addressed and reflected in both functional and non-functional specifications.

Bibliography

P. Kranas, P. Martinez, J. Pereira, L. M. Garcia, G. Manias, E. Kouremenou, M. Patiño and A. Azqueta, “D3.3 – Primary data capture and ingestion I”, iHelp deliverable, October 2021.

G. Manias, U. Wajid, A. Dalianis and A. Azqueta, “D3.7 – Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogeneous Data I”, iHelp deliverable, October 2021.

G. Marinos, G. Manias, A. Pnevmatikakis, N. Mehandjiev and U. Wajid, “D2.1 – State of the art and requirements analysis I”, iHelp deliverable, June 2021.

F. Melillo, “D2.4 – Conceptual model and reference architecture I”, iHelp deliverable, August 2021.

A. Pnevmatikakis, S. Spanos, A. Perikleous, H. op den Akker, P. Kranas, U. Wajid, C. Orton, “D3.5 – Secondary data capture and interoperability I”, iHelp deliverable, October 2021.

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DSS	Decision Support System
EU	European Union
FPG	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCP	Health Care Professional
HDM	Hospital de Denia-MarinaSalud
HHR	Holistic Health Record
IAM	Identity and Access Manager
IM	Identity Manager
ID	Identifier
JDBC	Java Data Base Connectivity
M	Month
MUP	Medical University Plovdiv
PC	Pancreatic Cancer
REST	Representational State Transfer
T	Task
TMU	Taipei Medical University
UC	Use Case
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UNIMAN	University of Manchester
WP	Work Package

Annex A. API Documentation

A.1 Data Connector

The Data Connector is the component that can be considered as the barrier between the iHelp integrated solution and the external data sources, from which it will capture the data to be pushed into the established data ingestion pipeline. During the first phase of the project, it can be considered as a standalone Java process that is responsible to establish the connectivity mechanisms to the external data sources and forward them to the data ingestion pipeline, by invoking the Data Gateway via REST API (see section A.2). The java process will include a thread containing a servlet container that can be used to configure and administrate the data connector. Therefore, this component will expose some REST web services that will allow that data provider to interact with the data gateway. At a later phase of the project, the REST API might be removed and the data provider might need to interact with the serverless platform itself, which will take the responsibility to invoke the corresponding functionalities.

The following subsections define the list of the designed REST APIs that are currently being implemented at this phase of the project. They might be extended or completely removed at the second phase, thus the second version of this deliverable will provide their final definition.

It is important to be highlighted that the users of these web methods will be the data providers that need to perform an administrative task so that the data capture and ingestion process can start or can be scheduled. Although the web methods allow for the data administrators to start, stop or monitor the data ingestion process, they are not related with the actual deployment of the data gateway. The latter is the responsibility of the iHelp platform administrator and is irrelevant from the end-user how data gateway itself should have been deployed. Information about this can be found in the corresponding D3.3 deliverable (K., M., P. + 21). The following subsection give details about the external API of the gateway, that allows the data ingestion to start and stop, encapsulating its internal details.

Base URL: /connector

A.1.1 CaptureStart

It submits a job to immediately start a data capture process. It accepts a JSON body with the data capture required parameters (i.e. dataset name, connection type, schema of the dataset, etc).

Request

Method	URL
POST	/

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
body		<pre>{ "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "topic": "topic name, or can be</pre>	The arguments params are specific to the type of the

		<pre>omitted in case of the default", "schema": "the schema of the dataset in an Avro compatible format. This must be a JSON object", "arguments": "the connector specific arguments. This must be a JSON object" }</pre>	<p>connector. As this work is currently under development, there have not been finalized yet. More info will be given in D3.3 (K., M., P. + 21) and D3.4 – Primary data capture and ingestion I (M22)</p>
path	N/A		

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>{ "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted" : "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "finished" : "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "status": "STARTED/FINISHED/FAILED", "message": "error message", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType" : "REST/DB/FTP" }</pre>
400	{"error": "Bad request"}
404	{"error": Connector type does not exist}
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.1.2 CaptureSchedule

It submits a job to schedule a data capture process. It accepts a JSON body with the data capture required parameters (i.e. dataset name, connection type, schema of the dataset, etc).

Request

Method	URL
POST	/schedule

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
body		<pre>{ "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", }</pre>	The arguments params are specific to the type of the

		<pre> "topic": "topic name, or can be omitted in case of the default", "schema": "the schema of the dataset in an avro compatible format. This must be a JSON object", "arguments": "the connector specific arguments. This must be a JSON object", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } </pre>	<p>connector. As this work is currently under development, there have not been finalized yet. More info will be given in D3.3 (K., M., P. + 21) and D3.4 – Primary data capture and ingestion I (M22)</p>
path	N/A		

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre> { "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted": "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } } </pre>
400	{"error": "Bad request"}
404	{"error": "Connector type does not exist"}
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.1.3 GetAllJobs

This method returns all submitted jobs. The result will be a list of all submitted jobs.

Request

Method	URL
--------	-----

GET	/
-----	---

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
path	N/A		

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>[{ "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted": "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } }]</pre>
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.1.4 GetJobByID

This method returns information for the job with the given id.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
path	id	UUID-XXX-XXX	The unique identifier of the job

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>{ "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted": "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } }</pre>
400	{"error": "Bad request"}
404	{"error": "id does not exist"}
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.1.5 StopJobById

This method stops a currently running job, according to its id.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/stop

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
path	id	UUID-XXX-XXX	The unique identifier of the job

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>{ "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted": "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, </pre>

	<pre> "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } </pre>
400	{"error": "Bad request"}
404	{"error": "id does not exist"}
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.1.6 GetAllScheduledJobs

This method returns all scheduled jobs. The result will be a list of all scheduled jobs.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/schedule

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
path	N/A		

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre> [{ "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted": "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } }] </pre>
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.1.7 GetScheduledJobByID

This method returns information for the scheduled job with the given id.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/schedule

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
path	id	UUID-XXX-XXX	The unique identifier of the job

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>{ "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted": "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } }</pre>
400	{"error": "Bad request"}
404	{"error": "id does not exist"}
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.1.8 StopScheduledJobByID

This method stops a currently scheduled job, according to its id.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/schedule/stop

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Not defined yet		
path	id	UUID-XXX-XXX	The unique identifier of the job

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>{ "id": "UUID-XXX-XXX-XXX", "submitted": "1970-01-01 00:00:00", "dataset": "DatasetXYZ", "connectorType": "REST/DB/FTP", "schedule": { "future": { "time": 2, "unit": "hours" }, "periodic": { "time": 1, "unit": "week" } } }</pre>
400	{"error": "Bad request"}
404	{"error": "id does not exist"}
500	{"error": "The message of the exception"}

A.2 Data Gateway

The Data Gateway microservice exposes a REST API through which the iHelp connectors can send their data to the iHelp platform.

Base URL: /data_gateway

A.2.1 DataReceiver

It receives the data from the data collectors and transforms them into a Kafka message.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	api_key*	String	Must be sent with all client requests. The api_key helps the server to validate the request

			source
body	payload*		The data to be forwarded to the data pipeline for further processing in JSON format.

Response

Status code	Response
200	No response
500	{"error": "Something went wrong. Please try again later."}

A.3 Data Cleaner

Data Cleaner will be utilized as an integrated microservice in the overall iHelp project, and its main objective is to deliver the software implementation that will provide the assurance that the provided data coming from several heterogeneous data sources will be clean and complete, to the extent possible. This microservice will be designed to minimize and filter the non-important data, thus improving the data quality and importance.

A.3.1 Asynchronous communication

The Data Cleaner consumes data asynchronously from a Kafka topic and directly produces data asynchronously to another Kafka topic. For interacting with the Kafka topic, it uses the corresponding Kafka client libraries to firstly establish a connection and then to consume and produce messages to the corresponding Kafka topics. Regarding the interaction with the Kafka message bus, the Data Cleaner is considered as a consumer listening to one Kafka topic in order to consume raw data fetched and produced by the Data Gateway (see section A.2) and as a producer providing cleaned data to another Kafka topic. On top of this, regarding automated deployments of the overall data ingestion pipeline, the name of the topic can be received during run-time and might be dynamically sent by the serverless platform.

A.4 Data Qualifier

The goal of the Data Qualifier component is to automatically categorize both known and unknown data sources to specific reliability levels. To this end, this microservice seeks to provide a predictive selection mechanism for achieving data source's reliability during runtime providing a trustfulness of the connected data sources. The Data Qualifier sub-component classifies data sources as reliable and non-reliable both during the primary and secondary data injection.

A.4.1 Asynchronous communication

The Data Qualifier component will be implemented using Kafka Streams. Thus, it consumes data asynchronously from a Kafka topic and directly produces data asynchronously to another Kafka topic. More specifically, this sub-component receives the input message to its system by subscribing to a Kafka topic the file names of the cleaned and faulty data produced by the Data Cleaner sub-component (see

section A.3). Finally, the Data Qualifier sub-component output is published to a Kafka topic. The output is composed by the reliability data sources values and the cleaned data file name or the stored cleaned data file names in case of streamed data. As also presented in the Data Cleaner component, regarding automated deployments of the data ingestion pipelines, the name of the topic can be received during run-time and might be dynamically sent by the serverless platform.

A.5 Data Harmoniser

The Data Harmoniser will be utilized as an integrated microservice in the overall iHelp platform. It seeks to support and harmonize data coming from heterogeneous sources into a common format. To this end, its main aim is to provide annotated/correlated health data & harmonize them with the HHR format.

A.5.1 Asynchronous communication

The Data Harmoniser microservice will be utilized in an asynchronous way. This microservice will be integrated with the provided message bus mechanism, the Kafka, and it will consume and produce corresponding messages to the provided Kafka queues. The message to be consumed should be cleaned and qualified data, which will be further harmonised, transformed and mapped, hence an annotated, transformed and HHR format aligned message will be the output of this specific microservice and will be produced and sent to the corresponding Kafka topic/topics depending on the type of the data and the final mapping to the HHR format. More precisely, Data Harmoniser component internally consists of two more sub-functions responsible for the final mapping of the data to the HHR format, the Primary Data Mapper and the Secondary Data Mapper. To this end, these two sub-functions are the responsible ones for producing the final message to the corresponding Kafka topic in order this message to further consumed by the HHR Importer component.

- **Primary Data Mapper:** The Primary Data Mapper receives cleaned and transformed primary data directly from the Data Harmoniser. The health records received then are mapped to the HHR ontology-based records, through semantic matching and harmonisation techniques. After the necessary mapping / transformation process, the Primary Data Mapper produces and sends the new HHR record, through a Kafka topic to the HHR Importer component.
- **Secondary Data Mapper:** The Secondary Data Mapper receives cleaned and transformed secondary data directly from the Data Harmoniser. The interaction with the message bus, the Kafka, will allow the microservice to expose the converted data or the outcome of the mapping function to the provided message bus (Kafka) topic. The output of this microservice will be the data in the standardised HHR format. To this end, the Secondary Data Mapper microservice will serve as the final stage of the data cleaning and standardisation operation, before the data is passed on to the iHelp's Big Data Platform (see section A.12) through the HHR Importer component (see section A.6).

At this phase of the project, as also presented in the HHR Importer component, it has not been decided the exact number of topics on which Primary and Secondary Data Mappers need to produce the final mapped HHR data, as they are two design choices that are still under investigation:

- **Single topic:** All data that are being produced and sent to this topic have been previously transformed to HHR either by the Primary Data Mapper or by the Secondary Data Mapper.

- **Multiple topics:** The transformed to HHR data might concern different conceptual entities of the HHR model. Hence, there must be a different topic per defined HHR conceptual entity.

A.6 HRR Importer

This component is responsible for persistently store to the Big Data Platform (see section A.12) those data elements that have been initially captured by the data gateway, having being pre-processed and finally transformed to the iHelp's common data model, the HHR. It is the last function in the chain of the data ingestion pipelines. As such, once it has been deployed, it listens to a specific Kafka topic in order to receive those elements, and then interacts directly with the Big Data Platform in order to transform those HHR entities to data objects compliant with the defined relational schema of the datastore and finally persistently store them.

A.6.1 Asynchronous communication

The HHR importer, as being part of the data ingestion pipeline, it does not expose any REST API, but instead, it consumes data asynchronously from a Kafka queue and directly interacts with the BigData Platform. For interacting with the Kafka queue it uses the corresponding Kafka client libraries to firstly establish a connection and listen to one or more topics and then deserialize the incoming data to HHR entities. For interacting with the BigData Platform, it will make use of one of the available data connectivity mechanisms described in the section relevant with the BigData Platform. At the first phase of the project, it will make use of the JDBC driver, but in the second phase, it might exploit its direct API.

Regarding its interaction with the Kafka queue, the HHR Importer is considered as a consumer listening to one or more topics. At this phase of the project, it is not clear on how many topics it needs to listen to, as they are two design choices that are still under investigation:

- **Single topic:** As all data passing through this topic have been previously transformed to HHR, there HHR importer will only need to listen to a single topic.
- **Multiple topics:** Even if all data passing through this topic have been previously transformed to HHR, they might concern different conceptual entities of the HHR model. For instance, one dataset might contain demographic information about the persons/patients, another dataset might contain the results of their observations, while other datasets might contain information about their nutrition. Even if all these conceptual entities will be serialized according to the HHR definition, there might be the need to treat them differently in order for the implementation of the HHR Imported to be facilitated. In that case, there must be a different topic per defined HHR conceptual entity.

Finally, regarding automated deployments of the data ingestion pipelines, the name of the topic might not be known during the implementation phase, rather than being communicated to the HHR Importer during its deployment. As a fact, this information can be received during run-time and might be dynamically sent by the serverless platform.

A.7 Secondary Data Pre-processor

The Secondary Data Pre-Processor manages data arriving online from sensors or questionnaires, obtained outside a clinical setting, attempting to describe various aspects of everyday life.

Base URL: /1.2/health-api/

A.7.1 Patients

Get short details for all available patients.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/patients

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	status	{"active", "inactive"}	To query only inactive patients, fill status as inactive in Query Parameters. To query only active patients, fill status as active in Query Parameters. -- In the end of the endpoint: ?status=parameter

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "subjectIdentificationNumber": "string", "trialId": 0, "trackerId": "string", "birthDate": "2021-10-05T10:16:17.622Z", "sex": "string", "baselineDate": "2021-10-05T10:16:17.622Z", "terminationDate": "2021-10-05T10:16:17.622Z", "earlyTerminationDate": "2021-10-05T10:16:17.622Z", "status": "string" }</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.2 Patient details

Get patient details.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/patients/{id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	String	Patient short ID.

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre> { "subjectIdentificationNumber": "string", "timeZone": "string", "trackerId": "string", "baselineDate": "2021-10-05T10:23:04.577Z", "terminationDate": "2021-10-05T10:23:04.577Z", "earlyTerminationDate": "2021-10-05T10:23:04.577Z", "status": "string", "sex": "string", "birthDate": "2021-10-05T10:23:04.577Z", "height": 0, "weight": 0, "disease": "string", "severity": "string", "qtRobotId": "string", "metadata": [{ "title": "string", "codename": "string", "value": "string" }] }</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.3 Get Answered Questionnaires for Date

Get patient's answered questionnaires for the given date.

Request

Method	URL
--------	-----

GET	/patients/{id}/questionnaires/date/{referenceDate}
-----	--

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	String	Patient short ID.
path	referenceDate	String	YYYY-MM-DD

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre> { "patientId": "string", "questionnaires": [{ "questionnaireReference": "string", "refDat": "string", "healthentiaRecordId": 0, "data": [{}] }] } </pre>
400	Bad request
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.4 Get Patients Summary for Date

Get patient's daily summary for the given day.

Data types:

- Calories
- Steps
- Distance
- Floors
- Heart rate
- Active minutes
- Sleep stages

- Wear time

Request

Method	URL
GET	/patients/{id}/physical-data/pat1/date/{referenceDate}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	String	Patient short ID.
path	referenceDate	String	YYYY-MM-DD

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre> { "patientId": "string", "activities": [{ "refDat": "string", "actMSed": 0, "actMLight": 0, "actMFair": 0, "actMVery": 0, "actMOV": 0, "cals": 0, "distance": 0, "floors": 0, "hrRest": 0, "hrOut": 0, "hrFat": 0, "hrCar": 0, "hrPeak": 0, "stepNo": 0, "met": 0, "slLgtTim": 0, "slRemTim": 0, "slDeepTim": 0, "slWkTim": 0, "slDurTim": 0, "wearTim": true }] } </pre>
400	Bad request

401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.5 Get Patients Exercise Data

Get patient's exercises data for the given date.

Returns blank when no data found.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/patients/{id}/physical-data/pat2/date/{referenceDate}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	String	Patient short ID.
path	referenceDate	String	YYYY-MM-DD

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre> { "patientId": "string", "activities": [{ "refDat": "string", "actTyp": "string", "logType": "string", "cals": 0, "actMOvPa": 0, "actMSed": 0, "actMLight": 0, "actMFair": 0, "actMVery": 0, "met": 0, "stepNPa": 0, "distance": 0 }] }</pre>
400	Bad request

401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.6 Get Patients Physiology Data

Request patient's sample-based physiological data

Data types:

- Steps
- Distance
- Floors
- Elevation
- Calories
- ECG

Request

Method	URL
GET	/patients/physiology-data

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
body		<pre>{ "patients": ["string"], "types": ["string"], "from": "2021-10-05T10:39:08.464Z", "to": "2021-10-05T10:39:08.464Z" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre>[{ "patient": "string", "signals": [</pre>

	<pre> { "type": "string", "samples": [{ "datetime": "2021-10-05T10:36:49.649Z", "value": 0 }] } </pre>
400	Bad request
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.7 Get Patients Massive Data

Request massive data for all subjects or per trial for a date period.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/patients/massive-data

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
body		<pre> { "dateFrom": "2021-10-05T10:39:00.493Z", "dateTo": "2021-10-05T10:39:00.493Z", "trialId": 0 } </pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
400	Bad request
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.8 Profile

Get current user profile details.

Remarks:

- Shows available trials for this account.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/Profile

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre> { "id": "string", "firstName": "string", "lastName": "string", "email": "string", "organizationId": 0, "organization": "string", "timeZoneId": 0, "trials": [{ "id": 0, "name": "string", "codename": "string" }] }</pre>
400	Bad request
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.7.9 Login

Login and create new access token and refresh token.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/Login

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
body		<pre>{ "userName": "string", "password": "string" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "accessToken": "string", "refreshToken": "string", "expires": 0 }</pre>
400	Bad request
500	Server error

A.7.10 Refresh Token

Generates new access token with the given refresh token.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/RefreshToken

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
body		<pre>{ "refreshToken": "string" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>SUCCESS { "accessToken": "string", "refreshToken": "string", "expires": 0 }</pre>
400	Bad request
500	Server error

A.8 Personalised Predictor

The Personalised Predictor is responsible to deliver the necessary toolset that enables the usage of advanced AI learning techniques towards the development of a personalized health model.

Base URL: /predictor

A.8.1 RiskPredictor

Predict a patient's risk level with regard to the possibility to be diagnosed with PC.

The risk level refers to an enumeration of possible risk levels: *HigherThanAvg*, *Avg*, *LowerThanAvg*.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/risk

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	api_key*	String	must be sent with all client requests. The api_key helps the server to validate the request source
body	features	List<Feature>	A list of features related to pancreatic cancer risk factors.

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>{"risklevel": "HigherThanAvg"}</pre>

500	{"error": "Something went wrong. Please try again later."}
-----	--

A.8.2 SurvivalEstimator

Estimate a patient's cancer survival statistics as an overall N-year survival rate. Survival rates are given in percentages.

For an N-year survival rate a probability to survive per month is returned.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/survival

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	api_key*	String	must be sent with all client requests. The api_key helps the server to validate the request source
body	features	List<Feature>	A list of features related to pancreatic cancer risk factors.

Response

Status code	Response
200	{"m0": "0.13", "m1": "0.18", ..., "mn": "0.47"}
500	{"error": "Something went wrong. Please try again later."}

A.8.3 RiskFactorImportance

Estimate an importance score per risk factor related to the input features. A mapping between risk factors identified and their contributing/importance score.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/factors

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	api_key*	String	must be sent with all client requests. The api_key helps the

			server to validate the request source
body	features	List<Feature>	A list of features related to pancreatic cancer risk factors.

Response

Status code	Response
200	{"Smoking": "0.63", "GeneticMutation": "0.18" }
500	{"error": "Something went wrong. Please try again later."}

A.9 Analytics Workbench - Model Library

The Model Library is intended as a portion of a larger Analytics Workbench, as such some extra calls are detailed here.

Also within the Workbench models are viewed as applications so the terms 'model' and 'application' are used interchangeably in this document.

Base URL: /

A.9.1 Create Model

Creates the folders needed to store information about a model and generates an ID for the model.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/api/model/{modelName}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
body		{ "modelName": "nhsApp", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en" }	
path	modelName *	String	The name given to the model that's being generated

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.9.2 Edit Model

Creates a details.json file which contains the details for the model.

Request

Method	URL
PUT	/api/model/{modelId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
body		<pre>{ "modelName": "nhsApp", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en" }</pre>	
path	modelId *	String	The ID for the model that's being edited

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.9.3 Delete Model

Deletes a model based on the Model ID passed as a parameter.

Request

Method	URL
DELETE	/api/model/{modelId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	modelId *	String	The ID for the model that's being deleted

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.9.4 Get Models

Prints details such as Model name, date created and Social Media Source about all of the models.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/model

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "modelName": "app4", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "created": "2021-09-20T09:48:22.371Z", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en", "modelId": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "modelName": "nhsApp",</pre>

	<pre> "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "created": "2021-09-20T10:54:32.676Z", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en", "modelId": "67961705-79b2-4d0f-8998-3d292bb714ec" }] </pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.5 Get Model

Prints details such as Model name, date created and Social Media Source about a single app specified by the modelId parameter.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/model/{modelId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	modelId *	String	The ID for the model that's being retrieved

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre> SUCCESS { "modelName": "app4", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "created": "2021-09-20T09:48:22.371Z", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en", "modelId": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" } </pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.6 Create Rules

Creates a rules.json file using the request body as its contents.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/api/app/rules/{modelId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
body		<pre>{ "genericRules": [{ "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "polarity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }, { "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "subjectivity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }], "customRules": [] }</pre>	
path	modelId *	String	The ID for the model that the rules are being created for

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.9.7 Get Rules

Gets the data from the rules.json file of a specified model and outputs it as JSON.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/app/rules/{modelId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

path	modelId *	String	The ID for the model that the rules are being retrieved from
------	-----------	--------	--

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "genericRules": [{ "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "polarity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }, { "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "subjectivity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }], "customRules": [] }</pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.8 Get Alerts

Returns all of the alerts from the DataStore table 'alert_topic'.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", }]</pre>

	<pre> "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "238619a0-727e-4e3d-954a-1d473e14c3f6", "model_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "346e01be-1a28-44aa-91ac-07f7291a55d9", "model_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }] </pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.9 Get Alerts Paged

Returns all of the alerts from the DataStore table 'alert_topic'. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/page

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
	num	Int	Offset for the rows in the table. Default is 0
	size	Int	Number of rows retrieved. Default is 10

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre> SUCCESS [{ "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", </pre>

	<pre> "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "238619a0-727e-4e3d-954a-1d473e14c3f6", "model_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "346e01be-1a28-44aa-91ac-07f7291a55d9", "model_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }] </pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.10 Get Alerts by Model Paged

Returns all of the alerts from the DataStore table 'alert_topic' filtered by the model name specified by the model_id parameter. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/page/{model_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
	model_id *	String	The ID for the model that the alerts are being retrieved for
	num	Int	Offset for the rows in the table. Default is 0
	size	Int	Number of rows retrieved. Default is 10

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre> SUCCESS [{ "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", </pre>

	<pre> "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "238619a0-727e-4e3d-954a-1d473e14c3f6", "model_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "346e01be-1a28-44aa-91ac-07f7291a55d9", "model_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }] </pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.11 Get Alert Count

Returns all of the alerts from the DataStore table 'alert_topic'. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/count

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS [14]
422	Validation error

A.9.12 Get Alert Count by App ID

Returns all of the alerts from the DataStore table 'alert_topic' filtered by the model name specified by the model_id parameter. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/count/{model_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	model_id *	String	The ID for the model that the alerts are being retrieved for

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS [14]
422	Validation error

A.9.13 Get Events

Returns all of the events from the DataStore table 'event_topic'.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/events

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS [{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", }

	<pre> "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }] </pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.14 Get Events Paged

Returns all of the events from the DataStore table 'event_topic'. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/events/page

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	num	Int	Offset for the rows in the table. Default is 0
path	size	Int	Number of rows retrieved. Default is 10

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre>[{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\n•an end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\n•an end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.15 Get Events by ID

Returns the alert from the DataStore table 'alert_topic' filtered by the alert_id specified by the alert_id parameter.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/events/{alert_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	alert_id *	String	The ID for the alerts that the events are related to

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre> SUCCESS [{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }] </pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.16 Get Events by User

Returns all of the events from the DataStore table 'event_topic' filtered by the user id specified by the user_id parameter.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/events/{user_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	user_id *	String	The ID for the user that generated the events

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre>[{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "model_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.17 Get Keyword File

Gets the words from the keywords list indicated by the model_id and the list number (file_num) and outputs it as a JSON array.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/getfiles/{model_id}/{file_num}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	model_id *	Int	The ID for the model that the word list is being retrieved from
path	file_num*	Int	The ID for the user that generated the events

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>["health", "symptoms", "pancreatic", "iHELP", "care", "recommend"]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.9.18 Update Files

Updates the words from the keywords list indicated by the model_id and the list number (file_num) and outputs it as a JSON array.

Request

Method	URL
PUT	/getfiles/{model_id}/{file_num}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	model_id *	Int	The ID for the model that the word list is being retrieved from
path	file_num*	Int	The ID for the user that generated the events

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>["health", "symptoms", "pancreatic", "iHELP", "care", "recommend"]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10 Social Analyser

The Social Analyser component is responsible for the analysis of discussion taking place on the social media platforms in order to provide insight into the lifestyle trends, mental models, emotions, social interactions and societal influences on the individuals who either have developed the Cancer or are in the early stage of risk identification.

A.10.1 Create App

Creates the folders needed to store information about an application and generates an ID for the application.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/api/app/{appName}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

body		<pre>{ "appName": "nhsApp", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en" }</pre>	
path	appName *	String	The name given to the application that's being generated

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.10.2 Edit App

Creates a details.json file which contains the details for the application.

Request

Method	URL
PUT	/api/app/{appId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
body		<pre>{ "appName": "nhsApp", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en" }</pre>	
path	appId *	String	The ID for the application that's being edited

Response

Status code	Response
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200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.10.3 Delete App

Deletes an application based on the Application ID passed as a parameter.

Request

Method	URL
DELETE	/api/app/{appId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	appId *	String	The ID for the application that's being deleted

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.10.4 Get Apps

Prints details such as Application name, date created and Social Media Source about all of the applications.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/app/list

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>SUCCESS [{ "appName": "app4", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "created": "2021-09-20T09:48:22.371Z", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en", "appId": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "appName": "nhsApp", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "created": "2021-09-20T10:54:32.676Z", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en", "appId": "67961705-79b2-4d0f-8998-3d292bb714ec" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.5 Get App

Prints details such as Application name, date created and Social Media Source about a single app specified by the appld parameter.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/app/single/{appld}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	appld *	String	The ID for the application that's being retrieved

Response

Status code	Response
-------------	----------

200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "appName": "app4", "description": "", "social_media_source": "Twitter", "created": "2021-09-20T09:48:22.371Z", "query": "nhs", "lang": "en", "appId": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.6 Create Rules

Creates a rules.json file using the request body as its contents.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/api/app/rules/{appId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
body		<pre>{ "genericRules": [{ "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "polarity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }, { "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "subjectivity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }], "customRules": [] }</pre>	
path	appId *	String	The ID for the application that the rules are being created for

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
422	Validation error

A.10.7 Get Rules

Gets the data from the rules.json file of a specified model and outputs it as JSON.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/app/rules/{appld}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	appld *	String	The ID for the application that the rules are being retrieved from

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "genericRules": [{ "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "polarity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }, { "comparator": "lt", "comparator_field": "subjectivity", "comparator_value": "0.7" }], "customRules": [] }</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.8 Get Alerts

Returns all of the alerts from the Clickhouse table 'alert_topic'.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "238619a0-727e-4e3d-954a-1d473e14c3f6", "app_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "346e01be-1a28-44aa-91ac-07f7291a55d9", "app_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.9 Get Alerts Paged

Returns all of the alerts from the Clickhouse table 'alert_topic'. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/page

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
	num	Int	Offset for the rows in the table. Deafult is 0
	size	Int	Number of rows retrieved.

		Default is 10
--	--	---------------

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "238619a0-727e-4e3d-954a-1d473e14c3f6", "app_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "346e01be-1a28-44aa-91ac-07f7291a55d9", "app_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.10 Get Alerts by App Paged

Returns all of the alerts from the Clickhouse table 'alert_topic' filtered by the application name specified by the app_id parameter. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/page/{app_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
	app_id *	String	The ID for the application that the alerts are being retrieved for
	num	Int	Offset for the rows in the table.

			Default is 0
	size	Int	Number of rows retrieved. Default is 10

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre>[{ "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "238619a0-727e-4e3d-954a-1d473e14c3f6", "app_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }, { "created": "2021-09-20T14:45:25", "app_name": "app4", "user_name": "Artyannie", "user_id": "1132230860", "trigger": "text contains patient AND text contains health", "id": "346e01be-1a28-44aa-91ac-07f7291a55d9", "app_id": "e3d6eb19-506c-40e4-a780-592e7dc2007b" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.11 Get Alert Count

Returns all of the alerts from the Clickhouse table 'alert_topic'. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/count

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS [14]
422	Validation error

A.10.12 Get Alert Count by App ID

Returns all of the alerts from the Clickhouse table 'alert_topic' filtered by the application name specified by the app_id parameter. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/alerts/count/{app_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	app_id *	String	The ID for the application that the alerts are being retrieved for

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS [14]
422	Validation error

A.10.13 Get Events

Returns all of the events from the Clickhouse table 'event_topic'.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/events

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre> SUCCESS [{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }] </pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.14 Get Events Paged

Returns all of the events from the Clickhouse table 'event_topic'. The num parameter is used for the page number to determine the offset and the size parameter is how many alerts are retrieved from the table..

Request

Method	URL

GET	/api/events/page
-----	------------------

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	num	Int	Offset for the rows in the table. Default is 0
path	size	Int	Number of rows retrieved. Default is 10

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre>[{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.15 Get Events by ID

Returns the alert from the Clickhouse table 'alert_topic' filtered by the alert_id specified by the alert_id parameter.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/events/{alert_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	alert_id *	String	The ID for the alerts that the events are related to

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre>[{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75",</pre>

	<pre>"app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.16 Get Events by User

Returns all of the events from the Clickhouse table 'event_topic' filtered by the user id specified by the user_id parameter.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/api/events/{user_id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	user_id *	String	The ID for the user that generated the events

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre>[{ "alert_id": "c345231e-9f12-4f21-a027-63b6763d55ee", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\nan end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }, { "alert_id": "6f79d2e8-aae0-4ca1-843a-390dce98bfaa", "user_id": "171154445", "user_name": "senojus", "user_location": "Flintshire", "text": "RT @RichardBurgon: I have secured a debate in Parliament</pre>

	<pre>next week on the future of our NHS.\n\nI will be demanding:\n\n•an end to the creepin...", "created": "2021-09-20T13:38:48", "polarity": 0, "subjectivity": 0.06, "posneg": "positive", "found_word": "", "trigger": "polarity less than 0.75", "app_id": "b68f0876-1bf9-4926-8ea2-6d3ef97fc1ac" }]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.17 Get Keyword File

Gets the words from the keywords list indicated by the app_id and the list number (file_num) and outputs it as a JSON array.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/getfiles/{app_id}/{file_num}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	app_id *	Int	The ID for the application that the word list is being retrieved from
path	file_num*	Int	The ID for the user that generated the events

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>SUCCESS ["health", "symptoms", "pancreatic", "iHELP", "care", "recommend"]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.10.18 Update Files

Updates the words from the keywords list indicated by the app_id and the list number (file_num) and outputs it as a JSON array.

Request

Method	URL
PUT	/getfiles/{app_id}/{file_num}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	-		
path	app_id *	Int	The ID for the application that the word list is being retrieved from
path	file_num*	Int	The ID for the user that generated the events

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>["health", "symptoms", "pancreatic", "iHELP", "care", "recommend"]</pre>
422	Validation error

A.11 Monitoring and Alerting

Base URL: /

A.11.1 Rules Management - Get all alert rules

Get details for all available rules.

Request

Method	URL
--------	-----

GET	/alertrule
-----	------------

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	status	<code>{"active", "inactive"}</code>	To query only inactive alert rules, fill status as inactive in Query Parameters. To query only active alert rules, fill status as active in Query Parameters. -- In the end of the endpoint: ?status=parameter

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "alertTargetTypeId": 0, "alertTemplateId": 0, "code": "string", "compareConditionId": 0, "description": "string", "id": 0, "identifier": "string", "name": "string", "status": "string" }]</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.2 Rules Management - Get single alert rule

Get alert rule details.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/alertrule/{id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	Long	Rule ID

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "alertTargetTypeId": 0, "alertTemplateId": 0, "code": "string", "compareConditionId": 0, "description": "string", "id": 0, "identifier": "string", "name": "string", "status": "string" }</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.3 Rules Management - Add alert rule

Modify and update single rule.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/alertrule

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
body		<pre>{ "alertTargetTypeId": 0, "alertTemplateId": 0, "code": "string", "compareConditionId": 0, "description": "string", "id": 0, "identifier": "string", "name": "string" }</pre>	

		}	
--	--	---	--

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "alertTargetTypeId": 0, "alertTemplateId": 0, "code": "string", "compareConditionId": 0, "description": "string", "id": 0, "identifier": "string", "name": "string", "status": "string" }</pre>
400	Bad request
500	Server error

A.11.4 Rules Management - Modify alert rule

Modify and update single rule.

Request

Method	URL
PUT	/alertrule/{id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	Long	Rule ID
body		<pre>{ "id": 0, "alertTargetTypeId": 0, "alertTemplateId": 0, "code": "string", "compareConditionId": 0, "description": "string", "id": 0, "identifier": "string", "name": "string", "status": "string" }</pre>	

		}	
--	--	---	--

Response

Status code	Response
204	No content (successfully updated)
400	Bad request
500	Server error

A.11.5 Rules Management - Delete rule

Modify and update single rule.

Request

Method	URL
DELETE	/alertrule/{id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	Long	Rule ID

Response

Status code	Response
204	No content (successfully deleted)
400	Bad request
500	Server error

A.11.6 Monitoring - Evaluate rule against all patients on demand

Get a list of all patients that pass/fail a single rule.

Eval:

- "pass"
- "fail"

- “all”

Request

Method	URL
GET	/evaluate/rule/{id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	Long	Rule ID
body		<pre>{ "eval": "string" "from": "2021-10-05", "to": "2021-10-05" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "patientId": "string", "targetId":0, "targetname":0, "targetvalue":0, "alertValue":0 "date":"2021-10-05", "eval": "string" }]</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.7 Monitoring - Evaluate rule for a patient on demand

Report for a single patient for a single rule for a period.

Eval:

- “pass”
- “fail”
- “all”

Request

Method	URL
GET	/evaluate/patient/{patientId} /rule/{ruleId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	ruleId	Long	Rule ID
path	patientId	String	Patient ID
body		<pre>{ "from": "2021-10-05", "to": "2021-10-05" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "patientId": "string", "targetId":0, "targetname":0, "targetvalue":0, "alertValue":0, "date":"2021-10-05", "eval":"string" }]</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.8 Alerting - Generate alerts

Send alerts to patients, that has failed their personal goals, based on various alert rules.

Request

Method	URL
POST	/send/alerts

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
body		<pre>{ "from": "2021-10-05", "to": "2021-10-05" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.9 Alerting - Get alerts list

Get alerts for a patient for a period.

Request

Method	URL
GET	/alerts/patient/{Id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	Id	String	Patient Id
body		<pre>{ "from": "2021-10-05", "to": "2021-10-05" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	<pre>SUCCESS [{</pre>

	<pre> "patientId": "string", "date": "2021-10-05", "alertType": "string", "alertBody": "string" }] </pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.10 Feedback - Get Data

Return all aggregated data for certain parameter for a period

Get alerts for a patient for a period

Alert types:

- Steps
- Distance
- Floors
- Elevation
- Calories
- ECG

Request

Method	URL
GET	/history/type/{name}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	name	String	Type name
body		<pre> { "from": "2021-10-05", "to": "2021-10-05" } </pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	<p>SUCCESS</p> <pre> [{ "patientId": "string", </pre>

	<pre> "type": "string", "value": "string", "date": "2021-10-05" }] </pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.11 Feedback - Get Patient Data

Return all aggregated data for certain parameter for a patient for a period

Get alerts for a patient for a period

Alert types:

- Steps
- Distance
- Floors
- Elevation
- Calories
- ECG
- All

Request

Method	URL
GET	/history/patient/{id}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	id	String	Patient name
body		<pre> { "alerttype": ["string"], "from": "2021-10-05", "to": "2021-10-05" } </pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>[{ "patientId": "string", "type": "string", "value": "string", "date": "2021-10-05" }]</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.11.12 Feedback - Get Patient Motivation

Analyse patient aggregated data validate it against period target and produce / return list of motivational advice.

Report for a single patient for a single rule for a period.

Eval:

- "better"
- "worse"

Request

Method	URL
GET	/motivationaladvice/patient/{patientId}/rules/{ruleId}

TYPE	Params	Values	Description
head	Authorization	String	JWT Authorization header using the Bearer scheme.
path	ruleId	String	Rule ID
path	patientId	String	Patient ID
body		<pre>{ "from": "2021-10-05", "to": "2021-10-05" }</pre>	

Response

Status code	Response
200	SUCCESS <pre>{ "patientId": "string", "targetId":0, "targetname":0, "targetvalue":0, "alertValue":0, "currentValue":0 "date": "2021-10-05", "eval": "string" }</pre>
401	Unauthorized
500	Server error

A.12 Big Data Platform

This component is the central data repository of the overall iHelp integrated solution. It is based on the scalable relational database of LeanXcale, that offers a series of innovative features that can be exploited for either to support data ingestion in very high rates and to provide advanced analytical capabilities that can be further used by the analytical tools. As a relational data store, it supports the current SQL standard (ISO/IEC 9075:2016). In order to connect with the Big Data Platform, the client component must make use of one of the available drivers of the data store, or rely on integrated processing frameworks. To summarize the different ways for the client to connect, there are as follows:

- Java applications can direct connect using standard JDBC driver.
- .NET applications can direct connect using the relevant ODBC driver.
- For components written in python, they can make use of the python direct driver, and tools like SQLAlchemy.
- Components that make use of Apache Spark processing framework, they can rely on the corresponding Spark connector.
- For components that interact via Kafka topics, they can use the corresponding Kafka-connector.

All the aforementioned means for interacting with the Big Data Platform are either well-known standards, or rely on other processing frameworks. Therefore, the analytical descriptions of these standards and frameworks are outside of the scope of this report.

Last but not least, during the second phase of the project, it is planned to be released an additional driver that bypasses the relational query engine of the Big Data Platform and directly interacts with its storage engine. As the implementation of this driver is currently in progress, more details will be given in the second version of this report.